

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. ADVEN SHELLA ESPARTERO - ANTIQUANDO

English Instructor

Negros Oriental State University

Guihulngan, English Department

adven.antiquando@gmail.com

“GUIDED BY HIS LIGHT: A JOURNEY OF FAITH AND STRENGTH”

In darkest night, when all seemed lost, He shone so bright,
Guiding mine steps with His radiant light, through every plight.
Through winding ways and shadows cast, His love did last,
His grace a beacon vast, leading me steadfast.

When I was lost and spirits low, in sorrow's deep flow,
He lifted me with tender care, His love did show.
With gentle hands, He held me tight, through the longest night,
Restoring hope, igniting light, making all things right.

In moments weak, when strength was spent, and I was forspent,
He whispered soft, "Be not forspent," His message sent.
His power flowed, mine heart renewed, with courage imbued,
In every trial, His strength ensued, my fears subdued.

When dreams seemed far, beyond mine ken, and hope was thin,
He made a way, His love did then, my faith within.
Impossible turned possible, His miracles full,
With faith in Him, all things are full, my soul made whole.

Through every storm, He calmed the sea, His presence near,
Embracing me with love so dear, dispelling fear.
With every step, His hand in mine, a journey divine,
A path so blessed, by love benign, His light did shine.

So now I walk, with faith so strong, in Him I belong,
In Him, mine heart, where I belong, my eternal song.
For He's the light that guides mine way, both night and day,
Mine strength, mine hope, each passing day, come what may.

When trials come and shadows loom, His light breaks through,
With steadfast love, He sees me through, my heart renew.
In every challenge, great or small, His strength I call,
With Him beside me, I stand tall, and never fall.

In gratitude, my heart does sing, His praises ring,
For all the blessings He does bring, my everything.
With faith in Him, my path is clear, no need to fear,
For He is always ever near, my Savior dear.

